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Rasim-5. O'ng qo'l: II-III-IV-Y panja barmoqlarining nekrozi.

Xirurgik davodan keyingi 4 kun uyiga javob berildi va yashash joyida davomuolajalarini davom qildirish, choklarini 10-11 kunlari olish tavsiya qilindi.

Chok ornidagi-yaqinidagi to'qimalar nekrozi. Birinchi koruvdagi - tikilgan jaroxat o'rnidagi o'zgarishi natijalari: chap soning ichgi yuqoro 3/1 qicmida (10-14 sm xajmidagi) koagulyatsion nekroz sohasi kuzatiladi. Qobiq ostidan ajralish yo'q. Nekrotik to'qima atrofida aniq demarkatsiya chizig'i hosil bo'lgan (1-rasm). Klinik ko'rinishga asoslanib, 2024-yil (xirurgik infeksiya bo'limida, kasalxonaga yotqizilganining to'rtinchi kuni) jarrohlik davolash amalga oshirildi: tikilgan choklar olindi va nekrektomiya amaliyoti (nekrotik to'qimalarni teri osti yog' qatlamigacha tozalandi) amaliyoti bajarildi. Jaroxat chetlaridagi terining bir qismiga ikkilamchi choklar qo'yildi va qolgan (5,5 x 3,5 cm. maydonga teri ko'chirib o'tqazilli (6-rasm).

Rasim-6. Chap son yuqori 3/1 qismi, ichki yuzasi chok o'rni va atrof to'qumalarining nekrozi. a) oldingi ko'rinishit, b) nekreytamiyadan keyingi ko'rinishi.

Teri transplantatsiyasidan keyingi 7 chi kuni jaroxat o'rniterining yaxlit-ligi to'liq tiklandi.

Kuyishlardan keyingi nekroz; Bu kuyishdan keyin (termik, kimyoviy, elektr, nurlanishdan) shikastlanish agentining ta'siri tufayli yuzaga keladigan to'qimalarning (teri, mushak, suyak) o'limi. Bu chuqur kuyish chandiqlari, deformatsiyalar va funktsional buzilishlarni o'z ichiga olgan murakkab davolashni talab qiladi. Nekroz dermadan suyak to'qimasigacha turli chuqurliklarda paydo bo'lishi mumkin va uning darajasi kuyishning og'irligi va davomiyligiga bog'liq. Chuqur kuyishlardan keyin, funktsional buzilishlar: Bo'g'imlarning harakatlanishining cheklani, kosmetik nuqson-lar, deformatsiyalar bilan bog'liq muammolardan biri. Gipertrofik va keloid kuyish chandiqlari shifokorlar va bemorlar uchun katta muammo keltrib chiqaradi. Manbalardagi ma'lumotlarga ko'ra bu bolalarda 41% tashkil qiladi. Bolalardagi kuyishlardan keyingi yana bir muamm, bu bola tana hajmi o'sishi bilan ortadi, ammo chandiqlik hajmi o'smaydi va jarayon yanada kuchayadi. Bu jiddiy muammo murakkab rekonstruktiv jarrohlik jarayonini talab qiladi. Bizga murojat qilib kelgan bemorda shunga o'xshash xolar qayt etildi. Yashash joyida davo muolajalarini uzoq vaqt olgan va chap qo'l tirsak bo'g'umidan, panja ucti va barmoqlarigacha chuqur kuyish chandiqlari, deformatsiya va funktsional buzilishlar bilan murojat qilib keldi (rasim-7).

Rasim-7. Chap qo'l bilak, panja barmoqlarning kuyushdan keyingi nekrozi. 2-ki bosqichli nekrektomiyadan keyingi ko'rinishi.

Beborning umumiy ahvoli qoniqarli, keyingi davo muolajalarini davom qildirish uchun, plastik jarrohlik bo'limiga otkazildi.

Davolash. Barcha bemorlarni davolash yuqumli kasalliklar bo'yicha mutaxassis, reanimatsiya bo'yicha mutaxassis va jarrohlar tomonidan birgalikda amalga oshirilishi shart. Bu shoshilinch bo'lishi va to'rtta tamoyilga asoslangan bo'lishi mumkin:

1. Yiringli fokusni radikal jarrohlik yo'li bilan tozalash.
2. Antibakterial terapiya.
3. Mahalliy terapiya, dori vositalari va fizio terapiya.
4. Intensiv terapiya, hayotni qo'llab-quvvatlash choralari va ekstrakorpo-ral detoksifikatsiyani ta'minlash.

Xulosa. Yumshoq to'qimalar nekrozi (infektsiyasi) keng tarqalgan, bu juda og'ir holat bo'lib, o'lim darajasi 10% gacha. Ushbu maqolada bolalar yoshida tananing turli sohalarida bo'ladigan turli xildagi nekrozlar va ularni muvaffaqiyatli davolash holati keltirilgan. Jarayonining rivojlanishi, kelib chish sabablari, tasnifi, bakteriologik, rentgenografik va ultratovush tekshiruvlari, klinikasi va davolash tamoyillari berilgan. Bemorlarni davolashda: Kasallikning klinik ko'rinishiga, qo'shimcha diagnostik vositalarga, laborator taxlillariga asoslangan xolda, konservativ, operativ 1-2 bosqichli nekrekreptomiyasi va operatsiyadan keyingi jaroxatlarni mahalliy to'qima bilan tiklashga qaratilgan bir nechta jarrohlik amaliyotlari bajarildi. Jarrohlik davodan tashqari, bemorga antibakterial terapiya, turli maxamlar va immuno stimulyatsiya qiluvchi terapiyalar berildi. Bizda davolangan, katta maydonda nekrektamiya qilingan bemorlarning ba'zi-lari, keyingi davo muolajalarini davom etirish maqsadida plastik jarrohlik bo'limiga o'tkazildi. Bir so'z bilan aytganda yumshoq to'qimalarning nekrozlovchi infeksiyasini, fasisitni davolash yaxshi natijaga erishildi.

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VITAMIN D DEFICIENCY AS A PREDICTOR OF INFLAMMATORY ACTIVITY IN CHILDREN WITH ACUTE RHEUMATIC FEVER

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ANNOTATION

Background: Acute rheumatic fever (ARF) remains a significant pediatric health concern in developing countries. Recent studies suggest that vitamin D plays an important immunomodulatory role in inflammatory diseases.

Objective: To investigate the relationship between vitamin D deficiency and inflammatory cytokines (IL-1 β , IL-6, IL-8, IFN- γ) in children with acute rheumatic fever.

Methods: The study included 60 children aged 5–15 years diagnosed with ARF. As part of this study, the concentration of 25(OH)D in children with acute rheumatic fever (ARF) was evaluated and compared with data from healthy children of the same age group. Serum levels of 25(OH)D and proinflammatory cytokines were measured before and after treatment. Vitamin D levels were assessed by ELISA, and cytokines were determined using Vector-Best immunoassays.

Results: A significant inverse correlation was observed between serum vitamin D levels and IL-6 concentrations ($r = -0.42$, $p < 0.05$). The majority of children with severe carditis presented with pronounced vitamin D deficiency and elevated IL-6 and IFN- γ levels. After treatment, cytokine levels decreased while vitamin D status modestly improved.

Conclusion: Vitamin D deficiency may serve as a predictor of inflammatory activity in ARF and correlates with elevated proinflammatory cytokines, particularly IL-6. Assessing vitamin D status may help in the early detection of immune-mediated activity in children with ARF and guide preventive and therapeutic strategies.

Keywords: acute rheumatic fever, vitamin D deficiency, IL-6, cytokines, children, inflammation, immune response.

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ДЕФИЦИТ ВИТАМИНА D КАК ПРЕДИКТОР ВОСПАЛИТЕЛЬНОЙ АКТИВНОСТИ У ДЕТЕЙ С ОСТРОЙ РЕВМАТИЧЕСКОЙ ЛИХОРАДКОЙ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Введение: Острый ревматический лихорадочный синдром (ОРЛ) остается серьезной проблемой детского здравоохранения в развивающихся странах. Недавние исследования показывают, что витамин D играет важную иммуномодулирующую роль при воспалительных заболеваниях.

Цель: Исследовать взаимосвязь между дефицитом витамина D и воспалительными цитокинами (ИЛ-1 β , ИЛ-6, ИЛ-8, ИФН- γ) у детей с острым ревматическим лихорадочным заболеванием.

Методы: В исследование были включены 60 детей в возрасте 5–15 лет с диагнозом острая ревматическая лихорадка (ОРЛ). В рамках исследования оценивалась концентрация 25(OH)D у детей с острой ревматической лихорадкой (ОРЛ) и сравнивалась с данными здоровых детей той же возрастной группы. Уровни 25(OH)D и провоспалительных цитокинов в сыворотке крови измерялись до и после лечения. Уровни витамина D оценивались методом ИФА, а цитокины определялись с помощью иммуноферментного анализа Vector-Best.

Результаты: Была обнаружена значительная обратная корреляция между уровнями витамина D в сыворотке крови и концентрациями ИЛ-6 ($r = -0,42$, $p < 0,05$). У большинства детей с тяжелым кардитом наблюдался выраженный дефицит витамина D и повышенные уровни ИЛ-6 и ИФН- γ . После лечения уровни цитокинов снизились, а уровень витамина D незначительно улучшился.

Заключение: Дефицит витамина D может служить предиктором воспалительной активности при ОРЛ и коррелирует с повышенными уровнями провоспалительных цитокинов, особенно ИЛ-6. Оценка уровня витамина D может помочь в раннем выявлении иммуноопосредованной активности у детей с острой ревматической лихорадкой и определить стратегии профилактики и лечения.

Ключевые слова: острая ревматическая лихорадка, дефицит витамина D, ИЛ-6, цитокины, дети, воспаление, иммунный ответ.

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**O'TKIR REVMATIK ISITMA BO'LGAN BOLALARDA YALLIG'LANISH
FAOLIYATINING PREDIKTORI SIFATIDA D VITAMINI YETISHMAYDIGANLIGINI
BAHOLASH**

IZOHNOMA

O'tkir revmatik isitma rivojlanayotgan mamlakatlarda bolalar salomatligining muhim muammosi bo'lib qolmoqda. So'nggi tadqiqotlar shuni ko'rsatadiki, D vitamini yallig'lanish kasalliklarida muhim immunomodulyator rol o'ynaydi.

Maqsad: O'tkir revmatik isitma bilan og'rigan bolalarda D vitamini yetishmasligi va yallig'lanish sitokinlari (IL-1 β , IL-6, IL-8, IFN- γ) o'rtasidagi bog'liqlikni o'rganish.

Usullar: Tadqiqotda ARF tashxisi qo'yilgan 5-15 yoshli 60 bola ishtirok etdi. Ushbu tadqiqotning bir qismi sifatida, o'tkir revmatik isitma bilan og'rigan bolalarda 25(OH)D konsentratsiyasi baholandi va shu yoshdagi sog'lom bolalarning ma'lumotlari bilan taqqoslandi. Davolashdan oldin va keyin 25(OH)D va yallig'lanishga qarshi sitokinlarning zardobdagi darajasi o'lchandi. D vitamini darajasi ELISA yordamida baholandi va sitokinlar Vector-Best immunoassaylari yordamida aniqlandi.

Natijalar: Zardobdagi D vitamini darajasi va IL-6 konsentratsiyasi o'rtasida sezilarli teskari korrelyatsiya kuzatildi ($r = -0.42$, $p < 0.05$). Og'ir kardit bilan og'rigan bolalarning aksariyati D vitamini yetishmovchiligi va IL-6 va IFN- γ darajasining oshishi bilan og'rigan. Davolashdan so'ng, sitokin darajasi pasaygan, D vitamini holati esa biroz yaxshilangan.

Xulosa: D vitamini yetishmovchiligi yallig'lanish faolligini bashorat qiluvchi omil bo'lib xizmat qilishi mumkin va yallig'lanishga qarshi sitokinlarning, ayniqsa IL-6 ning oshishi bilan

bog'liq. D vitamini holatini baholash RI bilan og'rigan bolalarda immunitet vositasida faollikni erta aniqlashga yordam beradi va profilaktika va terapevtik strategiyalarni boshqaradi.

Kalit so'zlar: o'tkir revmatik isitma, D vitamini yetishmovchiligi, IL-6, sitokinlar, bolalar, yallig'lanish, immun javob.

Acute rheumatic fever (ARF) develops as a result of a complex interaction of various factors. The acute inflammatory process affects the joints, brain, cardiac muscle, and/or skin, and is caused by an atypical immune response. While the clinical manifestations of the disease may resolve completely, cardiac involvement (carditis) can lead to **chronic rheumatic heart disease (RHD)**, which is associated with serious complications and can be potentially fatal [1,3].

It has been established that **vitamin D exerts selective effects** on various groups of innate immune cells, modulating their development, metabolic activity, antigen-presenting capabilities, and the production of signaling molecules such as cytokines and chemokines [7,9,11].

Vitamin D deficiency is a widespread problem affecting public health globally, particularly among children [4,5,12]. Studies indicate that vitamin D may influence the immune system and reduce inflammation in various infectious and autoimmune diseases. In a small number of studies involving pediatric patients, decreased serum concentrations of 25(OH)D were observed in children with autoimmune disorders.

The incidence of upper respiratory tract infections peaks during the winter and spring months, when 25(OH)D levels are expected to be at their lowest due to reduced sun exposure. Additionally, children aged 5 to 15 years undergo active growth, increasing their need for vitamin D [10].

Cytokines are key immune mediators that play a crucial role in the pathogenesis of autoimmune diseases⁷. In recent years, a growing body of evidence has demonstrated the involvement of proinflammatory cytokines in the development of ARF and RHD [7,8]. Among the most studied mediators whose levels are significantly elevated in the systemic circulation of patients with ARF and RHD are **interleukin-6 (IL-6)**, **interleukin-8/CXCL8**, and **tumor necrosis factor-alpha (TNF- α)**.

Adequate serum concentrations of 25(OH)D are associated with increased levels of anti-inflammatory cytokines, such as **interleukin-4 (IL-4)** and **interleukin-10 (IL-10)**, and with decreased levels of proinflammatory cytokines like **IL-1** and **IL-6** [3].

Objective: The aim of this study was to investigate the relationship between vitamin D deficiency and pro-inflammatory cytokines in children with acute rheumatic fever (ARF).

Study Design: This cross-sectional study involved 96 children aged 5 to 18 years, who were divided into two main groups. Group 1 included 60 children diagnosed with acute rheumatic fever based on the modified Jones criteria; Group 2 consisted of 36 healthy children matched by age and sex. The study was conducted at the multidisciplinary clinic of the Samarkand State Medical University (SamSMU), in the pediatric department, from 2024 to April 2025.

Methods: Vitamin D levels were determined by enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) using the EUROIMMUN 25-OH Vitamin D ELISA kit (E150519BY) manufactured by EUROIMMUN AG. The reproducibility of the test meets international standards, and its correlation with reference methods (high-performance liquid chromatography and IDS ELISA) is recognized as very high. The ELISA kit was used semi-manually, and results were evaluated using a calibration curve.

Cytokine levels were assessed by immunoassay (ELISA) using a standard commercial reagent kit from HEMA (Russia). The vitamin D tests were conducted in the biochemical laboratory of the multidisciplinary clinic at SamSMU.

Results: The study included children with acute rheumatic fever (ARF) aged 5 to 18 years. The majority were children aged 5 to 9 years, accounting for 24.7% (n=37); children aged 10 to 14 years comprised 10.7% (n=16), and those aged 15 to 17 years made up 4.63%. Among the age group 10–14 years, girls predominated, whereas boys were more numerous in the 5–9 year age group.

Given the existing data on the pathogenetic relationship between vitamin D deficiency and ARF, it was deemed appropriate to analyze the seasonal variations of the disease in children. A

prospective analysis of ARF incidence revealed that the peak prevalence occurred during the winter-spring months (Fig. 1).

Gender analysis showed a slight predominance of girls (51.7%) compared to boys (48.3%) among the examined patients (Fig. 2).

In the group of 60 children with ARF under our observation, serum vitamin D levels were analyzed using liquid chromatography (see Table 1).

Table 1.
Distribution of Vitamin D Levels in Children with ARF and Healthy Children
(ng/mL)

Vitamin D Level (ng/mL)	Children with ARF (n = 60)	%	Healthy Children (n = 36)	%
0–20 (Severe deficiency)	13	21.7%	3	8.4%
20–30 (Deficiency)	34	56.7%	7	19.4%
30–100 (Adequate level)	13	21.7%	26	72.2%

Based on serum vitamin D levels, children were divided into three groups. The first group (Group I) included children with severe deficiency — 13 children (21.7%), with a mean vitamin D level of 17.38 ± 0.93 ng/mL. The second group (Group II) consisted of 34 children (56.7%) with vitamin D deficiency, with a mean level of 23.90 ± 0.44 ng/mL. The third group (Group III) included 13 children (21.7%) with adequate vitamin D levels, with a mean concentration of 45.10 ± 4.80 ng/mL. Thus, 78.4% of children with ARF had either a deficiency or a severe deficiency of vitamin D.

Table 2.
Results of Correlation Analysis Between Vitamin D Levels and Interleukin Levels in Children with ARF

Parameters	Spearman's ρ	Strength of Correlation (Cheddock Scale)	p-value
Vitamin D – IL-1 β	-0.282	Weak	< 0.001*
Vitamin D – IL-6	-0.701	Strong	< 0.001*
Vitamin D – IL-8	-0.147	Weak	0.072
Vitamin D – IFN- γ	-0.154	Weak	0.061

* Differences are statistically significant ($p < 0.05$).

Statistical Analysis: Statistical analysis was performed using the software StatTech v. 4.6.3. Quantitative variables were tested for normality using the Kolmogorov–Smirnov test. The direction and strength of correlations between two quantitative variables were assessed using Spearman's rank correlation coefficient (for non-normally distributed data). A predictive model characterizing the dependence of a quantitative variable on influencing factors was developed using linear regression analysis. Differences were considered statistically significant at $p < 0.05$. A weak inverse correlation was found between IL-1 β and vitamin D. An increase of 1 ng/mL in vitamin D was associated with a decrease of 0.036 pg/mL in IL-1 β . The resulting model explained 5.4% of the observed variance in IL-1 β . A strong inverse correlation was found between IL-6 and vitamin D. An increase of 1 ng/mL in vitamin D was associated with a decrease of 0.069 pg/mL in IL-6. The model explained 25.7% of the observed variance in IL-6. A weak inverse correlation was observed between IL-8 and vitamin D. An increase of 1 ng/mL in vitamin D was associated with a decrease of 0.038 pg/mL in IL-8. The model explained 3.5% of the observed variance in IL-8.

A very weak inverse correlation was found between IFN- γ and vitamin D. An increase of 1 ng/mL in vitamin D was associated with a decrease of 0.004 pg/mL in IFN- γ . The model explained 0.0% of the observed variance in IFN- γ .

Discussion. In the studied cohort of patients with acute rheumatic fever (ARF), the majority were children of primary school age (5–9 years), accounting for 24.7% ($n = 37$) of the total sample. The proportion of patients aged 10–14 years was 10.7% ($n = 16$), while adolescents aged 15–17 years represented the smallest group at 4.63% ($n = 7$). These findings are consistent with literature data indicating that ARF most commonly manifests between the ages of 5 and 15, with peak incidence occurring in the younger age groups¹².

Of particular interest is the gender distribution across different age categories. Among children aged 5–9 years, boys predominated, whereas among those aged 10–14 years, girls were more frequently affected. These differences may reflect variations in immune responses, hormonal status, and the influence of environmental or lifestyle factors on the risk of developing ARF at different stages of childhood.

Analysis of the overall gender structure among patients with ARF revealed a slight predominance of girls — 51.7% ($n = 31$) compared to 48.3% ($n = 29$) boys, yielding a female-to-male ratio of 1.06:1. Other studies have shown that the initial incidence of ARF does not demonstrate significant sex-related differences; however, the progression rate of rheumatic heart disease is reportedly higher among females¹³.

Both the ARF and control groups demonstrated a high prevalence of vitamin D deficiency and insufficiency. Children with ARF had significantly lower mean serum concentrations of 25(OH)D compared to the healthy controls.

It has been established that within inflammatory processes, the interaction between vitamin D and the cytokine profile plays a key role in promoting a pro-inflammatory state via several molecular mechanisms. In our study, an inverse correlation was found between serum 25(OH)D levels and the concentration of the pro-inflammatory cytokine IL-6 in children with ARF. We also observed weak inverse correlations with IL-1 β , IL-8, and IFN- γ . These findings suggest that vitamin D may suppress IL-6 secretion by monocytes and macrophages through inhibition of the p38 MAPK signaling pathway via the induction of MKP1. It is known that the MAPK pathway is activated by various stress stimuli and initiates the production of pro-inflammatory cytokines not only in immune cells but also in cardiomyocytes.

Conclusion. The results of this study suggest the possible involvement of inflammatory and/or immune-mediated mechanisms associated with vitamin D deficiency in the pathogenesis of acute rheumatic fever (ARF). A significant correlation was found between reduced vitamin D levels and elevated concentrations of interleukin-6 (IL-6), which plays a key role in the inflammatory response in ARF.

Among the risk factors for vitamin D deficiency in the pediatric population, the winter season stands out. The overlap between seasonal peaks in vitamin D deficiency and ARF incidence may further support the hypothesis that vitamin D insufficiency serves as a predisposing factor for the development of the disease.

Thus, vitamin D deficiency, accompanied by reduced immunomodulatory activity, may contribute to the activation of immune responses and the initiation of autoimmune processes in ARF. To gain a deeper understanding of the role of vitamin D deficiency in the pathogenesis of rheumatic fever and its impact on the clinical and immunological phenotype of the disease, large-scale prospective studies involving broader patient cohorts are required.

Fig.1. the seasonal variations

Fig.2. Gender analysis

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